

Horologium Augusti and the reckoning of Time

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We shortly discuss the Horologium Augusti in Rome and some literature about it. In particular, we will consider the astronomical link of this monument to the Ara Pacis, proposed by Edmund Buchner in 1976. About this link, some inconsistency had been pointed out by L. Polverini in his “Augusto e il controllo del tempo”. Some recent astronomical simulations will be discussed too.

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The item of Wikipedia [1] tells that “Horologium Augusti” is the other name of the Solarium Augusti, an ancient Roman monument in the Campus Martius constructed during the rule of Augustus. It functioned as a giant solar marker, according to various interpretations serving either as a simple meridian line [2] or as a sundial (Edmund Buchner's work [3]).

Erected by Augustus, the gnomon of it was the Egyptian red granite Obelisk of Montecitorio. This obelisk was coming from Heliopolis. In the Horologium, the gnomon was used to cast a shadow on a marble pavement "inlaid with a gilded bronze network of lines, by which it was possible to read the time of day according to the season of the year. The solarium was dedicated to the Sun in 10 BCE, 35 years after Julius Caesar's calendar reform. It was the first solar dedication in Rome [4]" [1].

The item [1] continues telling that the Solarium Augusti was a monument "integrated with the Ara Pacis in the Campus Martius, aligning with Via Flaminia, in such a way that the shadow of the gnomon fell across the center of the marble altar [Ara Pacis] on 23 September, the birthday of Augustus himself." No reference is given: as we will see in the following, this is a conclusion proposed by Edmund Buchner [3].

Wikipedia tells the two monuments, Ara Pacis and Horologium, must have been planned together, in relation to the pre-existing Mausoleum of Augustus, "to demonstrate that Augustus was "born to bring peace", that peace was his destiny.[5] According to the Cambridge Ancient History, "the collective message dramatically linked peace with military authority and imperial expansion." [6] En.wikipedia is also mentioning Pliny the Elder [7], who "remarked that in the course of time it [the Horologium] had become incorrect, and offered several explanations for the shift." We will see, in

the following, what was told by Pliny.

About Edmund Buchner's work, we read that he excavated some sections of the calibrated marble pavement of the Solarium Augusti under the block of houses between Piazza del Parlamento and Piazza San Lorenzo in Lucina. "Recent studies [by Peter Heslin] have challenged Buchner's reconstruction of the Solarium as a full sundial, maintaining that the archaeological and textual evidence indicates a simple meridian line, marking the changing noontime position of the Sun in the course of the year". [1,2]

Wikipedia in Italian Let us also consider Wikipedia in Italian [8]. Here we find a different and interesting approach to the Orologio di Augusto, that is the Horologium Augusti. Ref.8 is telling that it is the "Linea meridiana, la più grande del mondo antico", the meridian line, the largest of the ancient world. "Fu realizzato dall'imperatore Augusto servendosi dell'opera di Manlio Matematico, con un decreto del Senato del 13 a.C. per celebrare le conquiste della Gallia e della Spagna. Venne concluso nel 9 a.C." "All'estremità [dell'obelisco] vi era una sfera di bronzo che proiettava la sua ombra sulla Linea meridiana il mezzodì, indicando la posizione del Sole sull'eclittica (la stagione giorno per giorno)", that is, at the top of the obelisk there was a bronze sphere the shadow of which was showing the noon, and the position of the sun on the ecliptic (season, day after day). "Nel 1979, all'interno di una serie di cantine del Campo Marzio, fu rinvenuto ad una profondità di 8 metri un tratto dell'antica pavimentazione della piazza, riportante una linea graduata e iscrizioni in greco riferibili a simboli zodiacali" [3]. The item is referring to Buchner's work, and the fact that the archaeological works have discovered a graduated line and marks referring to the zodiacal signs. No "gilded bronze network of lines" is mentioned by [8].

Ref. 8 continues telling that two loci in the Natural History by Pliny exist, relevant for the discussion. However the item is just a draft, and therefore it is not precise. I suppose that the discussion given by Wikipedia item [8] is a very short (too short) reference to [9-11].

"Plinio il Vecchio ne descrisse il funzionamento in due "loci" della sua monumentale opera. In uno di questi "loci" (Plinio il V. N.H. II, 35) egli spiega esattamente che dopo 365 giorni e un quarto la posizione dell'ombra della sfera ritorna nella sua posizione di 4 anni prima: si trattava da parte di Augusto della verifica del ciclo calendariale del calendario giuliano che era stato male applicato dal 44 AC in poi fino al 9 AC, appunto l'anno dell'inaugurazione dell'obelisco, quando le ombre della sfera indicarono che gli anni del ciclo giuliano erano 4 e non 3". Actually, Pliny is discussing the Horologium Augusti in one locus. In another locus he is mentioning how the sun is moving, in a discussion on the motions of the planets.

Pliny the Elder Here the locus in Pliny the Elder's work on the Horologium (Naturalis Historia,

XXXVI, 72 ss.): "Ei, qui est in campo, divus Augustus addidit mirabilem usum ad deprendendas solis umbras dierumque ac noctium ita magnitudines, strato lapide ad longitudinem obelisci, cui par fieret umbra brumae confectae die sexta hora paulatimque per regulas, quae sunt ex aere inclusae, singulis diebus decresceret ac rursus augeresceret, digna cognitu res, ingenio Facundi Novi mathematici. Is apici auratam pilam addidit, cuius vertice umbra colligeretur in se ipsam, alias enormiter iaculante apice, ratione, ut ferunt, a capite hominis intellecta."

Let us use also <http://www.perseus.tufts.edu/> The Natural History. Pliny the Elder, translated and discussed by John Bostock, M.D., F.R.S. H.T. Riley, Esq., B.A. London. Taylor and Francis, Red Lion Court, Fleet Street. 1855.

Pliny is discussing the stone monuments, in particular the obelisks.

CHAP. 15. (10.) — The Obelisk which serves as a dial in the Campus Martius.

“The one that has been erected in the Campus Martius has been applied to a singular purpose by the late Emperor Augustus; that of marking the shadows projected by the sun, and so measuring the length of the days and nights. With this object, a stone pavement was laid, the extreme length of which corresponded exactly with the length of the shadow thrown by the obelisk at the sixth hour on the day of the winter solstice. After this period, the shadow would go on, day by day, gradually decreasing, and then again would as gradually increase, correspondingly with certain lines of brass that were inserted in the stone; a device well deserving to be known, and due to the ingenuity of Facundus Novus, the mathematician. Upon the apex of the obelisk he placed a gilded ball in order that the shadow of the summit might be condensed and agglomerated, and so prevent the shadow of the apex itself from running to a fine point of enormous extent; the plan being first suggested to him, it is said, by the shadow that is projected by the human head. For nearly the last thirty years, however, the observations derived from this dial have been found not to agree: whether it is that the sun itself has changed its course in consequence of some derangement of the heavenly system; or whether that the whole earth has been in some degree displaced from its centre, a thing that, I have heard say, has been remarked in other places as well; or whether that some earthquake, confined to this city only, has wrenched the dial from its original position; or whether it is that in consequence of the inundations of the Tiber, the foundations of the mass have subsided, in spite of the general assertion that they are sunk as deep into the earth as the obelisk erected upon them is high.”

At Pliny’s time, the meridian was not working well. And the writer is mentioning some reasons for this fact. As we can see, Pliny is not mentioning any link of the monument to the Ara Pacis (in fact, Pliny is not mentioning the Ara Pacis in his books), or any astronomical reference to equinoxes or solstices, or to Augustus’ birthday.

Let us report the other locus, where Pliny is discussing the motion of the sun. Here we can find the Pliny’s observation mentioned by the item of Wikipedia in Italian, but, as previously told, it is

concerning the motion of Heavens, and not the Horologium Augusti.

In CHAP. 6. (8.) — Of the nature of the stars; of the motion of the planets.

"The path of the Sun consists of 360 degrees; but, in order that the shadow may return to the same point of the dial (18), we are obliged to add, in each year, five days and the fourth part of a day. On this account an intercalary day is given to every fifth year (19), that the period of the seasons may agree with that of the Sun."

Notes (18) and (19) to the translation are telling: (18) "Sed ut observatio umbrarum ejus redeat ad notas." According to the interpretation of Hardouin, "Ad easdem lineas in solari horologio." Lemaire, ii. 243. (19) This is an example of the mode of computation which we meet with among the ancients, where, in speaking of the period of a revolution, both the time preceding and that following the interval are included.

Augustus and the calendar Actually, Wikipedia [8] is pointing out a very important fact, when it is telling "si trattava da parte di Augusto della verifica del ciclo calendariale del calendario giuliano ... l'anno dell'inaugurazione dell'obelisco, quando le ombre della sfera indicarono che gli anni del ciclo giuliano erano 4 e non 3". It was, for Augustus, the verification of the time cycle of the Julian calendar, that had been badly applied from 44 BC onwards until 9 BC, precisely the year of the inauguration of the obelisk, when the shadow of the sphere indicated that the years of Julian cycles were four and not three [8].

The item [8] is explicitly linking the Horologium Augusti and the Julian calendar, and the adjustment of this calendar made by Augustus.

Augustus knew very well the discrepancy between the astronomical time and the calendar dates, that is, the fact that the reckoning of time, by means of the Julian calendar, had been not properly applied from 45 BC to 9 BC. As we have discussed in [12], because of a wrong interpretation of the Julian reform, leap years were applied on a cycle of three years and not on a cycle of four years. By an edict of 8 BC, Augustus stopped the insertion of leap years, until the astronomical time was in agreement to the calendar. The agreement was achieved in 8 AD.

Augusto e il controllo del tempo A fundamental article exists, which is stressing the difference between astronomical time and the Julian calendar, and which is discussing the debate about the Horologium and its link to the Ara Pacis. It is an article written by Leandro Polverini, about Augustus and the reckoning of time, entitled "Augusto e il controllo del tempo" [13].

In the article we find that the first occasion that Augustus had to solve the problem of the calendar, which was running wrong, happened after the death of Lepidus, in 12 BC, when Augustus became Pontifex Maximus. Therefore, he had both religious and political power to apply a reform of the

calendar. He was in the same position of Julius Caesar in 46 BC.

"Augusto gli successe [a Lepido] come pontefice massimo, cumulando così – come, a suo tempo, Cesare – i pieni poteri politici e religiosi. Poteva, dunque, ormai procedere a correggere l'applicazione erronea che per 36 anni si era fatta di un aspetto essenziale della riforma di Cesare; in effetti, il problema della correzione fu affrontato alla prima occasione tecnicamente adeguata, quella del 9 a.C. Si è già detto come, l'anno seguente, un editto di Augusto risolse il problema." [13]. The first occasion to revise the calendar was in 9 BC. "L'importanza dell'intervento di Augusto sul calendario non mancò di essere subito sfruttata in funzione di propaganda politica." [13]

According to Polverini, after 9 BC Augustus had two means for his propaganda, the calendar and the Horologium, the huge obelisk in Campus Martius.

In [13] we find also, reported in German and in Italian, a summary of Buchner's words. From Buchner's *Horologium Augusti* (1996), «Es bleibt bestehen, daß die Äquinoktienlinie, die Linie des 23. September, des Geburtstages des Augustus, in die Mitte der ara Pacis weist und daß h. A. und ara Pacis zusammen eine Geburtstagsanlage sind, konstituiert am 4. Juli 13 v. Chr., wenige Wochen vor dem 50. Geburtstag des Augustus. Dazu paßt, daß die ara Pacis und sicher auch das h. A. [...] am 30. Januar v. Chr., dem Geburtstag der Livia, eingeweiht wurden». That is, the 30 January was the birthday of Livia, Augustus' wife.

And also: “Nel quadro archeologico della connessione fra la meridiana, l'Ara Pacis e il Mausoleo, che caratterizza la sistemazione augustea del Campo Marzio settentrionale, l'asse portante della teoria è costituito – per quanto propriamente riguarda la storia del calendario – dalla «linea degli equinozi, quindi il 21 marzo o il 23 settembre. Si tratta di una linea retta, con l'esatta direzione ovest/est, che porta direttamente al centro dell'Ara Pacis» - the words between «» are from a Buchner's book in Italian - «Agli equinozi d'autunno abbiamo il genetliaco dell'imperatore. Nove mesi prima, il solstizio d'inverno [...] coincide con il di lui concepimento. L'intero impianto dell'Horologium, quindi, è correlato con l'Ara Pacis sulla base dei giorni del concepimento e della nascita dell'imperatore [...]. Nel giorno della nascita dell'imperatore – che, oltre tutto, è nato “paulo ante solis exortum” [...] – l'ombra, tra la mattina e la sera, si sposta di circa 150 m. fino a raggiungere il centro dell'Ara Pacis. In tal modo una linea diretta conduce dalla nascita di questo uomo alla pax, ed è chiaramente dimostrato come egli sia “natus ad pacem”». These are the words, in Italian, from Buchner, as reported from the “L'orologio solare di Augusto” in [13].

On the equinox of autumn we have the birthday of Augustus. According to Buchner, the whole set-up of the Horologium was linked to the Ara Pacis, by means of an equinox line, running in the exact cardinal east/west direction. This line was devised in order to have the shadow of the obelisk reaching the center of the Ara Pacis on Augustus' birthday.

Polverini continues in [13], with fundamental observations. In Polverini's work, it is stressed that

the Buchner's proposal, based on the synchronization between the dies natalis of Augustus and the fall equinox, is inconsistent. "L'inconsistenza del sincronismo del dies natalis di Augusto e dell'equinozio autunnale sarà stata ovviamente riconosciuta da molti, ma – per quanto riguarda le pubblicazioni – la prima a mia conoscenza nella quale sia stata presa in debita considerazione è, nel 1990, l'intervento critico di Michael Schütz" [14].

This inconsistency will obviously have been recognized by many, but - as far as publications are concerned - to Polverini's knowledge, the first publication in which it was taken into proper consideration is, in 1990, the critical discussion by Michael Schütz.

About the inconsistency, let us observe the following. First, we have to tell that, at the time of Augustus, the fall equinox was on 26 September (date given in the Julian proleptic calendar used for astronomical events). We can easily find this date by means of the astronomical software CalSKY, for instance. The historical date of Augustus' birthday is 23 September of 63 BC. Before 45 BC, Rome used the Republican calendar, a luni-solar calendar that was applied in a rather irregular manner. For this reason, it is impossible to know the specific date of Augustus' birthday in the proleptic Julian calendar [15]. In 45 BC, when the Julian Calendar was introduced, Augustus maintained the date of his birthday as the same of the Republican calendar. In any case, it is clear that Augustus was aware of the fact that he was not born on the equinox of autumn. This is, in my opinion, the main reason to consider the link between Augustus and the equinoxes as inconsistent.

In year 45 BC, Augustus' birthday was on 24 September (Julian proleptic calendar), according to the discussion given in [12]. Due to the wrong use of the historical Julian Calendar, the date in the Julian proleptic calendar corresponding to September 23, shifted from 24 to 26. Then, after the Augustus' reform of the calendar in 8 BC, the date shifted from 26 to 23 in 8 AD. If we imagine that the obelisk and Ara Pacis were planned to be linked on the equinoxes in the manner proposed by Buchner, it is clear that within a few years this plan would have been wrong. It would have been a failure, in particular for a person that wanted to show a full control of time. And this is the second reason to consider the Buchner's proposal as inconsistent.

Simulation in 3D A third reason is coming from some recent simulations proposed in [16,17], made by a team led by Bernard Frischer, Indiana University Bloomington. The result is the following. "Frischer and colleagues found that the sun would have appeared on top of the obelisk not on Augustus' birthday, but on Oct. 9, the annual festival of the Temple of Palatine Apollo. Though the find was surprising, Augustus did have a major connection to Apollo, his favorite deity and patron god" [16].

The simulation of light and shadows is made in a 3D digital reconstruction model of the Augustan Campus Martius. The model of that part of the Campus where the Ara Pacis was placed is based on

the excavation and reconstruction of the altar made by Giuseppe Moretti and Guglielmo Gatti, in 1937-38. For what concerns the obelisk, the positioning of it within the reconstruction required “an inferential method, whose results can be controlled by the data produced by unpublished corings undertaken by Edmund Buchner” [17]. As previously told, the Frischer’s simulations in his 3D reconstruction of the Campus Martius is giving another date, October 9, and not the equinox.

Actually, it is not clear from [17], what is the uncertainty of this result (at the same time, it is not given the uncertainty of the 3D model). Let us remember that the uncertainty is the experimenter's estimate of how far an experimental quantity might be from the "true value." Then, in this case, what is the uncertainty of “October 9”? Is it of a few hours, of a day, or of a few days? Without an uncertainty estimate, it is impossible to decide if the hypothesis can be confirmed or refuted.

In [17], we can read that the simulation was made on year 9 BC. A note of the article tells that the team was aware of the fact “that in that year, the calendar had not yet been re-synched to the leap year. That would not happen until AD 4. But the Romans were already aware of the problem and were addressing it. So the obelisk - Ara Pacis alignment will have been based on the corrected Julian calendar”. Then, according to Frischer, we have to imagine that, for some years, the link between obelisk and Ara Pacis appeared as planned in a wrong manner: a temporary failure for a future link between Augustus and the sun. Since the date obtained by the simulation seems to be the same of the festival of the Temple of Palatine Apollo, in [17] we find some discussion made to show that Apollo was the patron god of Augustus.

In [17], it is concluded that the monuments, obelisk and Ara Pacis, “were intentionally aligned and situated in order to propagate the same message as the one inscribed on two sides of the Montecitorio Obelisk ... : that Augustus was a devoted worshipper of the sun god (Sol), who brings Rome victory in war, peace, and prosperity through his earthly representative, the emperor.”

Actually, from archaeological excavations we have only that the obelisk was the gnomon of a huge meridian. Nothing more. The alignments proposed by Buchner and Frischer are just hypothetical alignments based on some coincidence of dates. Moreover, since the uncertainty of the result is not given, the proposed alignments are very questionable.

In conclusion, we have seen that during the Augustan period, the dates of the historical Julian Calendar are different from those we obtain in the proleptic Julian calendar [12]. Therefore, for what concerns the suggestions of astronomical alignments proposed for the monuments of that period, for instance as that mentioned by Buchner, we have to be very careful and consider the difference of the historical dates from astronomical time. At the same time, it is far from being obvious that the Romans planned astronomical alignments based on the corrected Julian calendar, when the calendar was out of synch.

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